

Effective tax rates of multinational corporations in European countries*

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Summary

1. Effective tax rates (ETRs) estimated from the income statement data of multinational corporations (MNCs) are useful for comparing MNCs' corporate income taxation across countries.
2. In a recently published paper, we propose a new methodological approach to estimate ETRs as reliably and for as many countries as possible using Orbis' unconsolidated data for the 2011–2015 period and 47 mostly European countries.
3. We find that ETRs substantially differ from statutory tax rates for some countries.
4. For example, we show that despite similar statutory rates of 28% and 29%, MNCs in Luxembourg paid as little as 1–8% of gross income in taxes, while those in Norway paid as much as 46–67%.
5. Despite being the best available, existing data is still imperfect. We therefore call for better data in the form of MNCs' unconsolidated, public country-by-country reporting data.

1. Introduction

Tax avoidance by multinational corporations (MNCs) contributes to inequalities both between and within countries. When MNCs shift profits to **tax havens**, other countries receive less profit and lower tax revenues

(Clausing, 2016, Nerudova et al., 2023). In case MNCs avoid taxes in a given country, the tax burden can be transferred to other taxpayers (Bilicka et al., 2023).

The **tax avoidance** has been addressed by the two-pillar proposal coordinated by OECD (2019b) and agreed as a common approach by more than 100 countries in 2021. Pillar 1

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(OECD, 2023) – similarly to other proposals in the European Union (European Commission, 2016, Petkova & Weichenrieder, 2020, European Commission, 2023) or globally (Picciotto, 2017) – would redistribute some MNCs’ profits according to economic activity.

Responding to tax avoidance, Pillar 2 takes a more direct approach to ensuring MNCs pay some taxes (OECD, 2023). It requires MNCs to pay a **minimum effective tax rate of 15%** in each country that implements it. In December 2022 the European Union has agreed for Pillar 2 to be mandatory for its members from 2024 and the taxes paid by MNCs are likely to increase as a result. But how much MNCs pay in corporate income taxes in various countries?

In a paper published recently by (Garcia-Bernardo et al., 2023) that this policy briefs draws on, we answer this question—what effective tax rates MNCs pay in individual countries—and provide some of the best available evidence for many countries worldwide.

2. Methods

In that paper, we strive to identify how much MNCs pay in corporate income taxes in various countries. We answer this question by estimating **effective tax rates** (ETRs) based on MNCs’ income primary statement data. These MNCs’ ETRs show how much MNCs pay in corporate income tax. In addition, we compare estimated ETRs across countries and we also compare them with statutory (or nominal) corporate income tax rates.

To provide as reliable ETR estimates as possible, we use unconsolidated data on MNCs provided by **Orbis**, which has the best data coverage for Europe and a good one, with at least 50 companies, for a total of 47 countries

worldwide. While we need to take into account some limitations of Orbis such as lack of detailed financial profit data that we discuss below, it is the database with the best European and worldwide coverage and with data concepts unified across countries. Additionally, in the absence of country-specific administrative tax data, Orbis is also likely the first choice of researchers and policy makers alike when it comes to measuring ETRs or evaluating the impact of reforms such as the global minimum tax.

Existing studies have attempted to answer our research question primarily by relying on one of two conceptually different approaches to ETRs. One uses a model of hypothetical companies developed on the basis of existing legislation (e.g. Devereux & Griffith, 1999, 2003), which results in **forward-looking ETRs**. On the one hand, these forward-looking ETRs have been estimated extensively, e.g. for EU member states (Spengel et al., 2014) or G20 countries (Congressional Budget Office, 2017) or OECD members (Cabral et al., 2021); they provide important policy insights and are useful in research. On the other hand, they seldom focus on MNCs and their estimates are by definition based on hypothetical modelling rather than on the observed behaviour of companies; as such, they are thus unsuitable to understand the *actual* tax rate that MNCs pay in a country.

The second approach uses data available for existing companies to develop **backward-looking ETRs** (or simply ETRs in this paper) which constitute our focus. In addition to Orbis that we use in our paper, the US-focused sources such as Form 5471 by Mutti & Grubert (2004) or Compustat by Markle & Shackelford (2012), Dyreng, Hanlon, Maydew, & Thornock (2017) or Schwab et al. (2022), are among the relevant data sources (reviewed more

comprehensively by, e.g., Janský, 2022). Furthermore, despite our focus on estimating backward-looking ETRs, we do compare them with one set of leading estimates of forward-looking ETRs prepared by the OECD (Hanappi, 2018). While the label of ETRs has been applied to several concepts, we believe that the potential of backward-looking ETRs has gone untapped thus far and that their use in research has been limited by their availability.

Our main contribution is **a new methodology** that estimates country-level backward-looking ETRs using the most extensive unconsolidated data of companies, Orbis, while being able to reflect carefully its limitations. As far as we know, this is the first paper explicitly dedicated to estimating ETRs from Orbis data for many countries, which enables us to do the estimation as thoroughly as possible. This contrasts with most existing literature, which estimated ETRs using Orbis as one of the steps in more complex research and they did not necessarily have a thorough methodology for this estimation that we strive to provide in this paper. Similarly to, for example, Egger, Loretz, Pfaffermayr, & Winner (2009), Fuest & Riedel (2012), or Johansson, et al. (2017), we use unconsolidated Orbis data to estimate ETR as the ratio of corporate income tax to gross income for all affiliates of MNCs in a given country, weighted by gross income. In contrast to any previous research, we propose four ETR estimations, including lower and upper bounds, which differ by gross income calculation. We outline the explanations for these four estimations in our paper and why any future research—interested in using unconsolidated Orbis data to estimate ETRs—should reflect them, regardless of which estimation they choose.

At present, no established source of such MNCs' ETRs is readily available or widely used. To the best of our knowledge, no reliable and continuously updated databases of ETRs estimated using company data are currently available. This lack of ETRs may be explained by both data- and methodology-related obstacles. For example, even the best available data sets suffer from poor accuracy and limited coverage. Even if the data were perfect, the very existence of multiple methodological approaches designed to estimate ETRs constitutes an issue in itself; furthermore, there is thus naturally less consensus on how to estimate ETRs than e.g., on how to determine the statutory tax rate. In this paper we overcome these challenges and fill the gap by developing a new methodological approach to reliably estimate ETRs for as many countries as possible. To do so, we provide newly estimated ETRs which shed new light on corporate taxation across many European and other countries and are relevant for tax reforms. To discuss the effects of any reform of the taxation of MNCs, we first need to establish the status quo, starting with **how much tax MNCs pay**. While our main goal is to provide a new methodology to estimate ETRs using Orbis data that can be used by other researchers (or against which they can benchmark their preferred methodology), we also apply the methodology to provide a new set of estimates.

3. Results

In this study we find that the amount of taxes accrued by MNCs varies considerably from country to country (Figure 1). Differences in ETRs were observed between individual countries. Out of the 47 countries and across the four ETR versions displayed in Figure 2, MNCs may expect to pay between 0% and 10% in 5 countries, 10–20% in 20 countries, 20–30% in 20 countries, and over 30% in 5

countries (and as little as 1% or as much as 65% in the most extreme cases) of their profit in taxes (numbers of countries are approximate due to the four versions of ETRs).

We also highlight **substantial differences between ETRs faced by MNCs and statutory corporate income tax rates** between 2011 and 2015 (Figure 2). As expected, ETRs are lower than statutory rates in most countries. This is expected in view of tax holidays and other tax provisions, which lead to ETRs being lower than statutory rates. As an extreme example, we show that despite similar statutory rates of 28% and 29%, MNCs in Luxembourg paid as little as 1–8% of gross income in taxes (for comparison, forward-looking ETRs of Luxembourg are above 20%, Hanappi, 2018), while those in Norway paid as much as 45–66% (driven mostly by the oil sector, as we discuss below).

Our novelty is not necessarily in highlighting which countries, such as Luxembourg, offer the lowest effective taxation as there is some research suggesting this using both narrow (e.g. Huesecken & Overesch, 2019, Tørsløv et al., 2022) and broader measures of corporate taxation (e.g. Keller & Schanz, 2013, Ates et al., 2021), but how low these ETRs in fact are. These ETRs also relate to Pillar 2 and our estimates indicate which countries might be affected by the minimum tax of 15%.

4. Conclusions

Overall, our results are the first to reveal the **actual extent of the differences between ETRs and statutory rates for many countries**. At the same time, existing evidence explains why ETRs are expected to be lower than statutory rates in most cases, or why ETRs of MNCs might be lower than of domestic firms, given the ample range of tax

credits and incentives provided by governments in the form of e.g. special economic zones, tax holidays or research and development tax credits (see, e.g., Klemm & van Parys, 2009, Shin, 2020, Bachas et al., 2023) and other characteristics of tax policy and MNCs including tax avoidance (Tørsløv et al., 2022) and territoriality (Liu, 2020).

Our results also suggest that **some EU countries do not tax MNCs much** and that, e.g., Luxembourg cannot lower its effective taxation much further since its ETRs are already close to zero. This is consistent with a race to the bottom with respect to ETRs and contributes to the existing evidence on it and its causes in the European Union and the rest of the world (Genschel et al., 2011, Abbas & Klemm, 2013, Crivelli et al., 2016, Clausing et al., 2020, Garcia-Bernardo, Janský, & Tørsløv, 2022).

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures

Figure 1. Effective tax rates in Europe. Notes: Mean and median ETR1 (defined in underlying paper) values in Europe. Countries with fewer than 50 companies per sample are not included in this figure. Source: Garcia-Bernardo et al. (2023)

Figure 2. Effective tax rates. Notes: Corporate income statutory tax rates (CIT), means and medians of ETRs in four estimations (ETR1–ETR4, defined in underlying paper) for 2011–2015, sorted by ETR3. Countries with fewer than 50 companies per sample are not included in this figure. Source: Garcia-Bernardo et al. (2023)

Further Information:

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